

Fear of Children's Literature: What's Left (or Right) After Theory?

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The year is 1944. As war rages in Europe and elsewhere, Americans can open a newly published book and read these words:

Children and grownups belong to different worlds. . . . How far removed is the world of childhood! Its inhabitants seem of another species. . . . Reason does not curb them, for they have not yet learned its restraints. Happy beings, they live in the clouds, playing light-heartedly without a care.¹

Not surprisingly, such beings require their own special kind of stories: "those that offer children an intuitive and direct way of knowledge, a simple beauty capable of being perceived immediately, arousing in their souls a vibration which will endure all their lives".²

The book expressing these convictions was *Books, Children, and Men*, a translation into English of *Les livres, les enfants, et les hommes*, first published in France in the early 1930s by Paul Hazard. From the viewpoint of 1995, it's hard to imagine that children could ever have been so innocent, or that children's books could ever have been so innocent—or, above all, that an adult could ever have been so innocent as to believe so wholeheartedly in that childhood innocence. It's especially hard not to remember that, as Americans read these words, children were starving and dying and otherwise being abused, not only in European concentration camps but also in many of the poorer parts of the United States—and that they continue to be so treated now, all these decades later.

But Hazard wasn't alone in his views. They represent ideas about children and literature that most people took for granted for many decades. I bought my own copy of *Books, Children, and Men* in the late 1970s, as a newcomer to children's literature wishing to find out what the respected authorities had to say about my newly chosen subject. I knew the book was respected because it was still in print, more than thirty years after its first American publication, and it remained in print for some years after that. Furthermore, it wouldn't take more than a quick browse through journals that

publish reviews of or articles about children's books to find comments similar to the ones by Hazard with which I began. A lot of people still share these views.

Yet much has happened since 1944. There has been half a century more of news about the astonishing persistence and prevalence of child abuse in all its despicable forms. There has also been half a century of developments in our theoretical understanding both of child psychology and of literature. Nowadays, it's pretty difficult for people to maintain the conviction that childhood is ever as innocent as Hazard wanted to imagine it always was. More significantly for those of us professionally interested in this subject, it's almost impossible to maintain that literature for children could ever be as simple, as direct, or even as wise as Hazard claims.

If anything, what we have come to know—and how we have come to think five decades later as a result of that knowledge—can encourage only one clear response in us to children's literature, perhaps to all literature. That response is, quite simply, fear. After having learned what theory has to tell us about the nature of childhood and the nature of literature, we can logically conclude only that literature in each and all of its forms and manifestations is very, very bad for children and other human beings.

And indeed, many people do reach that conclusion—or get uncomfortably close to it.

Most obviously, there are the censors: those people of every political stripe who are convinced that literature representing values other than the ones they themselves know to be right and true is incredibly dangerous and exceedingly powerful, and inevitably will pervert young readers' minds. If this logic is ever correct, then surely it is always correct. All children's literature is at least suspicious, if not downright horrifying.

But even those of us who are committed to freedom of speech and who know that children almost always grow up with a deep belief in their parents' or peers' values, no matter what books they read—even *we* aren't free from our fears about literature. Some of us believe that children who read too much of what we consider to be inferior or tasteless literature will themselves remain inferior and without taste, and so we deeply fear popular series like the *Babysitters Club* or *Goosebumps*. And some of us, deeply learned in our knowledge of theory and ineffably wise, have even deeper and more all-encompassing fears. We see literature, all literature, as a means of enmeshing children in repressive ideology. In an article I wrote a few years ago, in which I explored the similarities between the intellectual basis of the European colonial project, as described by Edward Said in *Orientalism*, and our common assumptions about childhood, I concluded that children's literature is best understood as a means by which adults claim power over children and force them to accept our repressive versions of who they really are. Scary stuff, that children's literature—very dangerous indeed. Maybe the only way to protect children from being ruined for life is to keep them illiterate—that, and drown all the TV sets.

In 1994, I gave a paper at a children's literature conference in the United States about a series of picture books by the American writer and illustrator David Wiesner. While Wiesner's books claim to be celebrations of the freed imagination, I argued that even they were profoundly manipulative and repressive. After the talk was over, a member of the audience, my friend Lois Kuznets—a critic who has done fine work of

revealing repressive ideologies in apparently harmless texts—asked this question: “Is nothing safe anymore? Is it *all* dangerous?”

My immediate, automatic answer was, “Yes, Lois, of course, it *is* all dangerous.” But I surprised myself by saying it, and I've been wondering about Lois's question ever since she asked it. It's a good question, and a very important one. Is there anything left worth salvaging after theory gets through with literature? Is the whole enterprise of adults providing texts for children ever anything but oppressive and repressive? *Can* it be?

I'd like to explore those questions here—and then try to find some answers to them.

Let me begin once more with Paul Hazard. When I was asked to talk about what's happened to our theoretical understanding of children's literature since 1945, my first thought was to reread his book—it seemed like an easy way to recall where we'd all come from. As I browsed through *Books, Children and Men* for the first time in almost twenty years, I found myself noticing things in it I didn't remember having noticed in 1977, and that I suspect no adult interested in children's literature in 1944 would be likely to have noticed at all. My knowledge of theories of various sorts was making the book seem different than I remembered it.

My strongest response was to Hazard's faith that some texts might “offer to children an intuitive and direct way of knowledge, a simple beauty capable of being perceived immediately, arousing in their souls a vibration which will endure all their lives.”³ This now bothers me on two accounts: what it says about children's literature, and what it says about children.

About literature: literary theories of many kinds, from reception theory to gender studies, has encouraged me to understand that texts, all texts, exist within a complex network of ideas and images and cultural values—and that includes apparently simple texts written for children. I can no longer believe that any text is ever direct or simple, and I've come to mistrust critics like Hazard who claim that some are. Hazard takes all of his own knowledge of French life and culture for granted when he assumes that young children will automatically read Charles Perrault's fairy tales as he does.

I also find myself noticing how strangely contradictory it is that Hazard offers detailed analyses of a number of the books he claims speak so perfectly and so directly to children, from Perrault's fairy tales to *Robinson Crusoe*. If they are so simple and so direct, why do they need to be explained?

Which takes me to what Hazard says about children. What children understand so intuitively needs to be explained to adults like me because, Hazard asserts, we adults have lost the ability to think like children. That's a doubly dangerous generalization. First, it *is* a generalization: surely not all children are alike in any way whatsoever, except in being young. Second, it assumes the shared likeness is a deficiency in relation to adults: if nothing else, it's surely a little insulting for us to assume that children, any children, are closer to nature than we are, less sophisticated, and therefore, presumably, less evolved.

As I read Hazard's descriptions of children and their reading, I found myself doing an act of translation. He might well be right, but not, I told myself, about actual

children who might actually be reading books—for the real children I know are nothing like that, and they are not freaks. Rather, these might be accurate descriptions of what reader-response theorists call *implied* readers: the imaginary constructs of ideal audiences that writers had in their minds when they wrote, and therefore implied in the contents of their texts, and that actual readers might need to transform themselves into, in order to make best sense of the texts. In other words, Hazard may have confused the cart and the horse. In order to celebrate a certain kind of text, he had to pretend there already existed an audience, now defined as essentially childlike, exactly suited to respond to it. But in point of fact, the text precedes, and might even help to create, the audience.

Obviously, my act of translation changes what was apparently harmless in Hazard's text into something deeply suspicious. If a text invites and requires a real child to become the ideal reader—the ideal child—it implies, then the text is manipulative. And if that ideal child represents an ideal I don't myself share, then I have no choice but to see the manipulation as dangerous—something to fear.

I certainly fear Hazard's view of childhood—and recognize it as a very popular one even now. In insisting that children are exactly opposite to adults, an alien species who belong in a different and presumably better world, proponents of this idea force me either to share their views and despise adults for not being childlike, or to disagree with them and despise children for not being fully evolved humans. Both positions insist that children are more significantly different from adults of their own species than similar to them. As Hazard suggests in the first sentence of his that I quoted, "Children and grownups belong to different worlds."

As I consider that sentence, I can't help but notice the parallel between Hazard's view of children as an alien species and the kind of thinking that led too many human beings to believe for too many centuries that, for instance, woman and men belong to different species, that white Europeans and black Africans belong to different species, that Englishmen and Frenchmen belong to different species. In this kind of thinking, the species are not only different but opposite in every way. If men are reasonable, women are intuitive, and if Europeans are pragmatic, then Africans live only for the day. The Other is always and inevitably the opposite—and Hazard's children are clearly opposite to adults in every important way: imaginative where adults have lost the ability to imagine, playful where adults insist on serious purposes even in their play. Childhood, says Hazard, "remains healthy because it has not yet reached the age for analysing the soul's emotions."⁴

Or to put it another way, adults are all sick—including the adult who wrote these words. For Hazard makes this comment in the midst of a carefully organized and presumably rational analysis. Thus we have to conclude that he, himself an analytical adult, is sick also—a sick being envying the health of those in a category so opposite to himself that he could not possibly enter it. For an adult cannot become a child, just as a white cannot become black or, except through extreme and still relatively rare measures, a man cannot become a woman. Thus, another thing Hazard's view of childhood shares with certain forms of racism or sexism is praise of those qualities that mark the other and opposite to oneself as a stick with which to beat oneself and one's kind.

Always, in this kind of thinking, there is more than a hint that what is being celebrated is, exactly, inadequacy, inhumanity, incapacity—the state of being less than completely human. Women are wonderful because they aren't restricted by the narrow confines of truth or rational logic, blacks are full of the joy of life because they don't have the corruptly sophisticated white sense of how the world really works, children are blissfully innocent because they're just too dumb (or, in this logic, too smart) to know any better—lucky things. As James Kincaid says in his remarkable book *Child Loving: The Erotic Child and Victorian Culture*, we see being childlike as “a kind of purity, an absence and an incapacity, an inability to do. . . . Unencumbered by any necessary traits, the emptiness called a child can be constructed any way we like.”⁵

And so Hazard, I see, constructed it to his taste—which was, mostly, to privilege and celebrate its emptiness. “It is sweet, sometimes,” he says, “to see the world again with a child's eyes.” He goes on to say, “It is true that they lure us away from the feast of ideas, taking no pleasure there themselves. They place small value on the abstractions that are so useful to our grown-up pastimes.” But it's clear that what he presents here supposedly as a qualification is exactly the reason why he wants to think like a child: “Let us admit that they have no skill in handling ideas. What they have is enough for them.”⁶ It would be enough for him, too, it seems, if only he weren't cursed with his awful adult superiority—the terrible knowledge of how very bad knowledge is. Thus he has it both ways: he is superior, and he knows how bad it is to be superior enough to hate it—which presumably makes him even more superior than the rest of us adults. This kind of thinking is still surprisingly common in children's literature criticism, in which sophisticated adults often celebrate the wonderful innocence of childhood.

If I fear this sort of thinking, and I find it so blatantly present in Hazard, then what am I to make of the children's books he prefers—that the many adult experts who still share his basic principles prefer? They are ones that celebrate the childlike as something directly antithetical to what we might normally see as mature or thoughtful or responsible. Their wisdom is to deny that most of what we usually consider to be true is wise. If children did indeed learn what it means to be childlike from these books as Hazard understands them, they would be learning to be proud of their immaturity, thoughtlessness, and irresponsibility. They would learn that it is good to be self-indulgent and egocentric and careless of the feelings or needs of others. I find myself asking why this should be seen as a good thing.

Hazard's own answer to that question is a little strange, I think, and once more suggests a profound degree of self-hatred. He says he admires books that provide children “with pictures, the kind that they like. . . . enchanting pictures that bring release and joy, happiness gained before reality closes in upon them, insurance against the time, all too soon, when there will be nothing but realities.”⁷ Children must be childlike, unreal, or else there is nothing but the brute horror of the bare truth, despicable and unbearable reality itself. I can't imagine anything more pessimistic or more life-denying. Hazard's paean of praise for the jolly, happy childhood he has imagined and tries so desperately to impose on children disguises an exceedingly negative and very ugly view of the world he knows as an adult. In teaching me how to see this aspect of Hazard, theory has taught me to fear all forms of praise for the

delights of childhood—and that means just about all children's literature.

At this point, I'm reminded again of theorists like James Kincaid and Jacqueline Rose, who talk about how and why we adults attempt to persuade children that our imaginary visions of childhood are true. Rose believes that the actual nature of childhood—she focuses particularly on children's confused experience of sexual desire—frightens adults. We protect ourselves from knowledge of the chaotic confusion children really experience by constructing images of childhood that eliminate everything threatening, leaving only what Kincaid described as “a kind of purity, an absence and an incapacity, an inability to do.”⁸ We then present the images we have constructed to children in their literature, in order to persuade them that their lives actually are as we imagine them to be. “If children's fiction builds an image of the child inside the book,” says Rose, “it does so in order to secure the child who is outside the book, the one who does not come so easily within its grasp.”⁹

Children's literature, then, represents a massive effort by adults to make children believe that they ought to be the way adults would like them to be, and to make them feel guilty about or downplay the significance of all the aspects of their selves that inevitably don't fit the adult model.

It's all too frighteningly easy to read Hazard from this point of view. He insists both that children are inherently and always imaginative, and also that they need help from adults in being imaginative—need the right kinds of books to feed their imaginations and the right kind of adults, supposedly childlike ones, to write those books. So it is adults who must write children's books. But as we've already seen, all adults are afflicted by reality, and cannot see as children see. Only one conclusion is possible: adults no longer childlike must imagine—invent, contrive, create, make up—how children *should* see, and then impose what they imagine upon children, lest children see the actual ugly truth and therefore force adults to acknowledge that it is in fact the only truth. Let us create a lie of childhood and then force children to believe in it.

Hazard gets very angry at most writers for children: “Entirely pleased with themselves, they offered the child books that represented themselves, with all their attributes thrown in.”¹⁰ Yet the books that he himself recommends, he admires exactly because they represent himself and his ideas of wisdom. He is himself one of the people he attacks.

From this point of view, obviously, the books Hazard admires are exceedingly dangerous ones—greatly to be feared. And yet, of course, the danger is unavoidable. For there is one other thing theory has taught me: the aspects of children's books I've been describing—that Hazard takes for granted as good and true, and that I fear as bad and dangerous—are always and inevitably present. There would be no children's books if we didn't believe children were different enough from adults to need their own special kinds of books; and of course it is adults—the ones with the ideas about just how it is that children differ—who write those books. All children's books always represent adult ideas of childhood—and inevitably, therefore, work to impose adult ideas about childhood on children.

Furthermore, the process works. Children do become what we believe they are; assumptions about childhood, like those of Hazard, have the potential to become

self-fulfilling prophecies. If we believe, as many adults do, that children are limited in various ways, then we deprive them of experiences that might make them less limited. If we believe that children have short attention spans, we won't expose them to long books. If we believe they cannot understand complicated language, we will give them only books with limited vocabularies. If we believe they are susceptible, we will keep them away from interesting books that may contain potentially dangerous ideas or attitudes. And if we believe they like only certain kinds of books, we won't give them access to other kinds. Deprived of the experience of anything more than the little we believe them capable of, children often learn to be inflexible, intolerant of the complex and the unconventional.

And clearly, children's literature plays an important part in this process. As a wide range of ideological theorists like Antonio Gramsci and Louis Althusser and Raymond Williams have suggested, and as John Stephens in particular has so persuasively pointed out in *Language and Ideology in Children's Fiction*, whatever else literary texts are, and whatever pleasure they may afford us, they are also expressions of the values and assumptions of a culture and a significant way of embedding readers in those values and assumptions—persuading them that they are in fact the readers that the texts imply.

The reader whom Hazard suggests good children's books imply is one who inuriates in a supposedly childlike freedom. Paradoxically, therefore, he implies the unsettling truth that good children's literature is that which constrains and represses children in the process of pretending to liberate them. To believe oneself childlike in this supposedly freeing way is to accept limited and limiting adult ideas—to be childlike rather than mature, simple rather than sophisticated, intuitive rather than reasonable, empty rather than full.

Writing before theory, then, Hazard neatly reveals all the ways in which theory has taught us to be suspicious of our assumptions about children and children's literature—why we might fear them. Too neatly, perhaps—you might well wonder why I have spent so much time attacking such an obvious target. I have done it simply because so much of what I read in Hazard could still appear in adult discussion of children's literature today—still does appear, albeit, perhaps, in less poetic and more scientific language, influenced by brands of developmental psychology and pedagogical theory whose unspoken and uncontested myths of origin are very much like the ideas and assumptions that Hazard expresses so boldly.

And they appear for a good reason. I find it hard to imagine a third position in addition to the one Hazard presents and the one that shows me the dangers of the one Hazard presents. Theory tells me to fear Hazard; logic tells me that as long as children's literature exists as an endeavor of adults, it will always emerge from adult representations of childhood, and therefore, will always be in some way what Hazard describes it as being. To attack Hazard and to learn to fear him is, in some fundamental way, to learn to fear the entire project of children's literature, its very existence.

Is there then any third way possible? That's what I'd like to consider next.

My first step beyond fear comes, I realize, as I think about whom or what I fear for.

If I talk about embedding children or constructing their subjectivity as misrepresentation or oppression or limitation of their full potential, I'm assuming the existence of a child larger than, outside of, and complete beyond the construction—a whole, unified, coherent being whose unity and completeness I am fearing for. To be repressed is to be forced to be less than this whole.

But another kind of theory has taught me that such a child could exist only outside of human consciousness—beyond human life as we know it and could ever possibly be aware of it.

Before what the psychoanalytical theorist Jacques Lacan calls the mirror stage, that moment in infancy in which a child identifies itself with its image in a mirror, Lacan imagines that the child lives in a posited but in actual fact unknowable and utterly seamless universe, and makes no distinction between itself and other things—it is whole, complete, unified in the most absolute of senses. This pre-oedipal stage sounds very much like Hazard's vision of childhood: a prelapsarian paradise before knowledge of distinctions and divisions intervenes. What's interesting is that for Lacan it occurs early in infancy, at the very moment when self-consciousness first develops; what Hazard views as characteristically childlike actually disappears for Lacan at the moment when a child becomes conscious of itself as a child—or, more exactly, as just a human being. What Hazard calls childlike, Lacan might well define as not yet quite human.

In the mirror stage, the child develops an ego, a sense of self, and does so by realizing that there are things outside it, such as the space around its image in the mirror. It perceives that it exists as a separate being only inside a context that is larger than itself, and that makes the child feel small in relation to it. Once we identify ourselves with the smaller versions of ourselves we see in the mirror, therefore, we are always conscious of ourselves as diminished, lacking a wholeness we once had, eternally striving for and never achieving it, as Hazard strives for but never achieves what he perceives as the blissful delights of childhood. The mirror image, then, constrains and constricts us—as I believe the images of children that appear in children's literature work to constrict the children they attempt to embed in their images of the suitably childlike—and as, perhaps paradoxically, Hazard's idea of childhood as prelapsarian bliss constricts less blissful real children. For prelapsarian wholeness is hard to imagine as anything but empty—a state less confusing and less complex than maturity. And it isn't much of a leap to conclude that children who are successfully embedded in the limited or empty images of the childlike offered in so many children's books might well feel diminished by them—defined as being *less*, as lacking.

Inevitably, furthermore, to be conscious of oneself in terms of the imagery of mirrors is to be divided. Lacan speaks of the “bipolar nature of all subjectivity.”¹¹ A self is both that which thinks or views, the separate, detached consciousness, and that which is being viewed or thought about. I am *that* which sees myself as *this*: in demanding and therefore confirming this relationship—a reader sees himself or herself as a character or an implied reader—literary texts for children play their part in establishing what Lacan calls “an alienating identity” built on what is only an “illusion of autonomy.”¹² We are both what the books have encouraged us to believe we are *and*

the reader thus encouraged, a separate being who thinks about and acknowledges the truth of that representation. To identify is to see oneself as something else in two senses—as being the thing seen *and* as being the one who does the seeing.

If Lacan is at all right, then this divided subjectivity is inevitable—is in fact, and exactly, human consciousness as humans of any age past early infancy always know it. To rail against it, to fear the ways in which books help to create it, is to rail against life itself—to hate the human condition.

I can put that in another, and much simpler, way. To fear texts because they embed children in ideology is to fear all of the social and communal aspects of human existence—and all the pleasures they offer.

To be embedded is to learn to understand oneself as a social being—in terms of the obligations and responsibilities one has toward others, and also in terms of the kinds of behavior acceptable to others that will allow individuals to survive and prosper as members of groups. To embed children is to encourage them to think of themselves as the kinds of people who can live and interact with and take pleasure from other people in the human community as currently constructed around them.

There can be no question about the fact that the demands of community can—indeed, inevitably do—repress individual freedoms and limit individual potential. But they are also and inevitably necessary as the medium of our mind-expanding and deeply pleasurable exchanges with each other. *All* societal interactions occur in a language of gestures and behaviors that allow us to express our private selves in the very act of replacing, and therefore repressing, those private selves. These social conventions are like any other language, and as repressive of choice as any language. In order to communicate within them, we must agree to use the signs and structures shared by others. If we choose to invent our own signs and structures, we will be both totally free and totally unable to communicate with anybody else. I conclude, then, that children who did somehow manage to escape the apparently fearful process of being embedded in ideology might indeed retain their freedom to be whole—but they would do so only at the cost of being involved in any way at all with other people. That's more fearful than losing a little freedom. What seems like the fearful repressive tendency of children's literature from one point of view is, from another point of view, its rich ability to provide children with a means of making enriching connections with other human beings.

There is still, of course, the danger of the mask becoming the face. It is possible, as I suggested earlier, that children encouraged by an adult world to see themselves as being childlike in a particular way might well *become* childlike in exactly that way.

Furthermore, it's unquestionably true that some of the most popular ways of being childlike, as conveyed by literature and the mass media, are decidedly repressive and exceedingly limiting. And it's also unquestionably true that powerful forces in mainstream culture work hard to impose these repressive and limiting ideas of themselves upon children. Witness, as just one example, the ways in which Disney films continue to confirm decidedly dangerous ideas about what desirable girls' and women's bodies should look like. Girls who accept these images, most often *unthinkingly*, as the one and only way to be attractive and powerful work very hard to conform themselves to these supposed ideals, at great expense and often at great

danger to their health. In fact, then, the real danger is *not* that literature might work to fragment childhood sensibility and provide children with a divided and incoherent view of themselves. It's just the opposite of that. It might persuade children that one particular and partial representation is the complete and only truth.

Theory, which has helped me to perceive and understand this problem, also suggests a possible solution to it: knowledge of theory.

Representations possess the fearful potential to repress and envelop us without our being aware of it only to the degree to which we are unconscious of the fact that they *are* representations—and therefore accept them as the way things naturally and obviously are. Althusser says:

It is indeed a peculiarity of ideology that it imposes (without appearing to do so, since these are "obviousnesses") obviousnesses as obviousnesses, which we cannot *fail to recognize* and before which we have the inevitable and natural reaction of crying out (loud or in the "still small voice of conscience"): "That's obvious! That's right! That's true!"¹³

The potential for freedom, then, comes in realizing that the obvious may *not* be true—may just be a representation, just one possible way of being out of a vast spectrum of other possible ways of being that one might consider, try on, adopt. In the matter of ways of being human, one has a choice only at the point at which one realizes one has a choice.

Theory taught me that. If it worked for me, then why can't it work for children?

I believe that it can. I believe, indeed, that we adults must do everything we possibly can to make children aware of the "obviousnesses" that texts work to impose on them and to give them the means to weigh and consider the implications of the subject positions that texts offer. If we are not to fear for what texts might do to them, in other words, we must teach them to be divided subjects in their reading and in their lives—to be involved as both implied readers of texts and critical observers of what texts demand of them in that process. The texts I refer to here include literature—and also all the physical and social representations and gestures and conventions that make up our life in society.

To read the world in this way is to *be* this way—divided, fragmented, always aware of how the faces one puts on are merely masks, how there is always more to us than whatever particular way we've decided to represent our selves to others (and therefore, presumably, to ourselves) at any particular moment. This is not I that you see standing here talking to you—it is the I that I have chosen to represent myself as today.

In discussing how we perceive ourselves in terms of gender, Judith Butler argues that it always a question of performance—that we become male or female by enacting in our minds and bodies our culture's ideas about maleness or femaleness. What's true of gender, an aspect of our self-perception, seems to me to be generally true of all aspects of our self-understanding. As representations, personalities are roles we put on and perform—and, perhaps, nothing more. We are, in fact, fragmentary, collections of roles or representations, each of which is merely partial, not unified at all. Rather than fear that fact and work toward some illusory utopia of unity and wholeness, we

might instead celebrate the fragmentary. We might simply revel in and rejoice in the playful possibilities of the various masks and roles we can choose to put on, and the various beings we can inconsistently, at various points, choose to become.

In the end, then, theory teaches me that a foolish consistency is indeed the hobgoblin of little minds—minds that foolishly choose to perceive themselves as littler than they actually are. There is really no such thing as a complete or whole or coherent individual—and that's something to celebrate, not something to fear.

If we can learn to celebrate it, and teach children to celebrate it, then children's literature can be a source of much more than fear. It can, in its various manifestations, offer children a vast repertoire of ways of being human to choose from, to play with, to celebrate.

All we adults have to do, then, is not to fear—to fear neither children nor books. Not to fear children means to trust their ability to make wise decisions and enjoy playful possibilities once equipped with the strategies for doing so—the knowledge of theory I've just talked about. Not to fear literature is to not eliminate from children's experience books whose representations personally distress us, but instead to allow children access to as wide a range of representations as possible, in books of all sorts from places of all sorts by people of all sorts.

If we can be that fearless, then children will indeed learn to belong to a different world than our current repressed and limiting world of grown-ups. But then we grown-ups will belong to that different world, too.

NOTES

1. Paul Hazard, *Books, Children, and Men*, trans. Marguerite Mitchell (Boston: Horn Book, 1944), pp. 1–2.
2. *Ibid.*, p. 42.
3. *Ibid.*
4. *Ibid.*, p. 167.
5. James Kincaid, *Child-Loving: The Erotic Child and Victorian Culture* (New York and London: Routledge, 1992), pp. 70–71.
6. Hazard, *Books, Children, and Men*, p. 166.
7. *Ibid.*, p. 42.
8. Kincaid, *Child-Loving*, p. 70.
9. Jacqueline Rose, *The Case of Peter Pan; or, The Impossibility of Children's Fiction* (London: Macmillan, 1984), p. 2.
10. Hazard, *Books, Children, and Men*, p. 3.
11. Jacques Lacan, *Écrits: A Selection*, trans. Alan Sheridan (New York and London: Norton, 1977), p. 10.
12. *Ibid.*, pp. 4, 6.
13. Louis Althusser, "Ideology and Ideological State Apparatuses," trans. Ben Brewster, in *Critical Theory Since 1965*, ed. Hazard Adams, and Leroy Searle (Tallahassee: University Press of Florida and Florida State University Press, 1986), p. 245.

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